

REGIONAL DISTRIBUTION OF PRIMARY OPEN-ANGLE GLAUCOMA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10325165>

Abstract. Among the eye diseases that are currently of great medical and social importance, glaucoma is the most important. Its prevalence in the world among people over 30 years of age is 1.7%, in Russia 1.1-5.8 per 1000 adults. In the world, the number of young people with glaucoma is only constantly growing. So, in 1996 it was 66.8 million people, in 2002 - 105 million people, while, according to forecasts, by 2010 it will reach 150 million people. In the nosological structure of primary vision, glaucoma occupies one of the first places in the world. Currently, glaucoma has developed into heredity, live mucositis, and iklim karabmok. Primary open-angle glaucoma is the most common of all forms of primary glaucoma. There are many studies on the problem of primary glaucoma, but information about the climatic, racial characteristics of glaucoma is mainly limited to a small number of studies conducted by foreign authors

Keywords: BOBG, glaucoma, heredity, race.

Relevance of the study

Primary open-angle glaucoma is the most common form of primary glaucoma. BOBG is one of the main causes of low vision and blindness around the world. There are many studies on the problem of primary glaucoma, but the information about the hereditary, racial climatic characteristics of glaucoma is limited to a small number of studies conducted by foreign authors. A study of the ethnic characteristics of glaucoma among the rural population is being carried out. Many authors emphasize that the distribution of various forms of glaucoma has ethnic characteristics. Thus, the open-angle form of glaucoma is diagnosed more often among Caucasians and Negroids, and the closed-angle form of glaucoma among Mongoloids. In addition, there are ethnic characteristics of the course of glaucoma in people of different races. In Negroids and Indians, the disease begins earlier than in Caucasians, on average 10 years, and develops faster. One of the most numerous races in the world is the Mongols. Based on the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the eye organ, angle-closure glaucoma is more common in Mongoloids. The prevalence of open-angle glaucoma in Mongolians is different, for example, in Mongolia, BOBG is very rare - 0.5%, and in Bangladesh, it has the highest prevalence of all forms of primary glaucoma (75%). At the same time, the information of different authors is very contradictory.

However, despite the undoubted importance of studying the problem of the spread of primary open-angle glaucoma among the rural and urban population, this issue has not been sufficiently studied both in the whole world and in our country. It accounts for 80.3% of all glaucoma cases. Thus, the problem of glaucoma in the Republic of Uzbekistan is as acute as in other regions.

Research purpose:

- To study the problem and to determine the ethnic characteristics of primary open-angle glaucoma among the rural population and the reasons for the increase of the disease.
- Establishing the relationship between the incidence of various forms of primary glaucoma and regional differences between rural and urban populations.

-Determining the ethnic characteristics of the structure of the eyes of healthy and sick rural residents with primary open-angle glaucoma.

- Determining the clinical appearance of primary open-angle glaucoma in the rural population.

Materials and methods. The object of this study is the population of rural areas diagnosed with glaucoma. In order to evaluate the epidemiological features of the spread of glaucoma and to evaluate the organization of primary specialized medical care for patients suffering from this pathology, it is necessary to calculate the following indicators according to the federal statistical report forms (forms No. 12, No. 30): the main level of glaucoma in the general rural population; share of glaucoma patients registered in ophthalmologists; providing the population with an ophthalmologist (individuals) per 100,000 people; regarding patients diagnosed with glaucoma during preventive examinations; the total number of registered patients with blind and impaired vision. To determine the correlation between quantitative variables, the Spearman rank correlation method is used.

Clinical characteristics of primary open-angle glaucoma depending on the region of residence: for example, at the age of 40-50, 1 person out of 1000 (0.1%) is affected, at the age of 50-55, the incidence is 1%, at the age of 60. age - 4%, age 70 - 8%, age 80 - 15%. Some authors emphasize the existence of genetic features of the glaucomatous process.

The rural population with a small population is distinguished by the diversity of a number of anthropometric and dermatoglyphic indicators determined as a result of anthropological research. In order to study the ratio of primary glaucoma forms in regional groups, we decided to analyze outpatient charts of rural population of Uzbekistan suffering from primary glaucoma.

Primary open-angle glaucoma is 3.8 per 1000 population, BOBG - 0.7, and mixed form of glaucoma - 0.6.

According to the iceberg rule, the actual incidence of glaucoma is significantly higher than the reported incidence.

Conclusion. Thus, the distribution of the main forms of primary glaucoma differs between rural and urban local populations. According to the American Glaucoma Society, 85% of patients with BOBG can be treated with drugs without resorting to surgical treatment, but for this, the doctor must make sure that the patient strictly adheres to the instillation regimen.

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